

Research

Climate change and biocrust disturbance synergistically decreased taxonomic, functional and phylogenetic diversity in annual communities on gypsiferous soils

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Rainfall and biocrusts are important sources of temporal and spatial environmental heterogeneity and niche differentiation for annual plants, a major component of diversity in drylands. Therefore, global change processes comprising shifts in rainfall timing and drought exacerbation, together with biocrust disturbance may affect species coexistence and result in disrupted diversity patterns. In this study, we experimentally evaluated the effects of the rainfall amount and timing as well as physical biocrust disturbance and their interaction on the taxonomic, phylogenetic and functional diversity of annual plant communities on gypsum soil drylands. All diversity estimates were determined at different times during community development in each experimental unit (α), as the contribution of each experimental unit to the total diversity in each treatment (β) and as the total diversity in each treatment (γ). Rainfall timings led to changes in all diversity dimensions, with higher diversity under the typical timing. The community was quite resilient to moderate reductions in rainfall, but extreme droughts decreased the alpha and beta taxonomic, functional and phylogenetic diversities. In addition, the simultaneous occurrence of biocrust disturbance and extreme drought led to consistent collapses in all diversity dimensions, probably because the effects of water shortage were exacerbated. Observations of the community at different times during its development highlighted the importance of regenerative strategies for niche differentiation and species coexistence, and their strong dependence on global change drivers. Indeed, our experimental study demonstrated that rainfall patterns and biocrusts are key factors related to the maintenance of diversity in semiarid annual plant communities. In particular, our results highlight the key role of biocrusts in modulating the effects of drought on plant diversity and the need for integrative approaches that consider both plants and biocrusts in order to elucidate the influence of climate change on the diversity of drylands.

Keywords: annual plants, biocrusts, climate change, diversity loss, drought, gypsum soil, Mediterranean ecosystems, rainfall timing, regeneration niche

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Introduction

Habitat heterogeneity in space and time enhances species coexistence (Chesson 2000) by increasing the availability of niches (Stein et al. 2014). To some extent, each species occupies a unique niche defined by the range of environmental conditions under which it can thrive throughout its ontogeny. A species niche is related to the ecological preferences and competitiveness of each species, and thus it is defined by its functional traits (Adler et al. 2013). This functional perspective allows each species to be characterized in terms of its niche occupancy and competitive ability based on its functional traits. Similarly, communities (i.e. realized assemblages) can be described according to the niche overlap and interactions among coexisting species (Levine and HilleRisLambers 2009) based on their functional structure. Furthermore, shifts in the community functional structure related to drivers of global change may lead to filtering processes excluding some species from realized assemblages (HilleRisLambers et al. 2012) and potentially result in diversity losses.

The niche of each species can be characterized by a set of functional traits related to some critical biological processes (Shipley et al. 2016). However, complete functional characterization is not always feasible, so the phylogenetic relatedness among species is often used as a proxy of their functional similarity (Swenson 2011). Phylogenetically related species are ecologically similar if traits are conserved during their evolution. Consequently, phylogenetic diversity (PD) may reflect the diversity of functional strategies in a more integrative manner than functional diversity (FD) (Adler et al. 2013). However, some previous studies avoided directly applying this assumption (Gerhold et al. 2015), whereas others emphasized the potential of using PD for forecasting the stability of communities under the effects of global change (Li et al. 2019).

Each dimension of diversity (taxonomic diversity (TD), FD and PD) can provide information about the different eco-evolutionary processes that are involved in the assembly of plant communities (Swenson 2011). Therefore, they offer a complementary perspective of the assembly mechanisms that can become even more comprehensive if diversity is described at different scales, including α , β and γ measurements (Graham and Fine 2008). Indeed, fine scale observations can provide direct information about plant–plant interactions, whereas larger scale data may give insights into processes related to environmental heterogeneity (Purschke et al. 2013), which are critical for the design of conservation measures under global change. The complementarity between the three dimensions of diversity for explaining the organization of communities is currently an emerging topic in ecology (Li et al. 2019, López-Angulo et al. 2020), but their covariation in realized assemblages is still poorly understood. Moreover, it is important to determine how drivers of global change might affect the three components of diversity and their covariation (González-Orozco et al. 2016).

In the present study, two well-known sources of spatial and temporal environmental heterogeneity for annual plants

(rainfall amount and timing, and cover of biological soil crust, biocrust hereafter) were experimentally manipulated according to global change scenarios. Most models predict that the future climate will be characterized by a higher frequency of extreme droughts, especially in Mediterranean-type climates (Barros and Field 2014). Changes in the occurrence of droughts may affect the community functional structure and the diversity of realized assemblages (Harrison et al. 2018, 2020). Moreover, the timing of rainfall can be equally or even more important for species compositions than the rainfall amount because it determines the time available for annual plants to complete their short (a few months) life cycles (Levine et al. 2011). In addition, biocrusts that mainly comprise lichens, cyanobacteria and mosses cover around 12% of the Earth's terrestrial surface (Rodríguez-Caballero et al. 2018), and they are critical components of drylands. Biocrusts greatly affect soil water runoff, infiltration and evapotranspiration (Eldridge et al. 2010, Chamizo et al. 2012, Kidron and Tal 2012, Berdugo et al. 2014), as well as nutrient dynamics (Elbert et al. 2012). Thus, biocrusts can interact with individual plants in many ways (Zhang et al. 2016, Havrilla et al. 2019) by providing different microhabitats throughout the ontogeny of plants (Concostrina-Zubiri et al. 2014) and affecting the assembly of annual communities (Luzuriaga et al. 2012, Kidron 2019). Drivers of global change also affect biocrusts (Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2014, 2016, Reed et al. 2016) and their degradation could have unknown consequences for these ephemeral grasslands. Annual plants provide an ideal model for the manipulation of a whole plant community, which is required to overcome the limitations of observational approaches when inferring causality in community ecology. Furthermore, the use of experimental communities has emerged as a powerful tool for testing the connections between assembly mechanisms and the different dimensions of plant diversity (HilleRisLambers et al. 2012). In the annual grasslands that grow on gypsum soils, the small size of the plants (mean maximum height of 10.5 cm in our study area) and richness (ca 38 plant species/0.25 m²; Luzuriaga et al. 2012) allows microcosms to be established by collecting soil monoliths containing seeds dispersed during the latent period (summer in our Mediterranean habitats). In addition, their short and synchronized life cycles (from their germination in autumn to reproduction and death in late spring) allow the key processes that prevail throughout the ontogeny of plants to be identified based on sequential observations of the community during its development. Environmental cues that drive germination (Sánchez et al. 2014) and plant–lichen specific interactions that drive seedling establishment (Escudero et al. 2007) are critical during the earliest community stages. Subsequently, the increased importance of abiotic restrictions imposed by low temperatures may be more relevant (Pescador et al. 2018). In the reproductive stage when the plant cover reaches its maximum extent, species interactions are increasingly important for the use of major resources such as water (Luzuriaga et al. 2012).

In the present study, our experimental approach and analysis of the three diversity dimensions at different times during

community development allowed us: 1) to experimentally determine the effects of the rainfall timing, increased drought and biocrust disturbance on the TD, FD and PD of annual plant communities; 2) to assess the importance of environmental filtering and niche heterogeneity as mechanisms that might allow experimental perturbations due to global change to modify the α , β and γ diversities; and 3) to obtain evidence regarding the prevalence of previously cited processes in different community life stages. The rainfall pattern can act as a filter during dry years or seasons, but it can enhance diversity by promoting temporal niche differentiation in different rainfall scenarios over time (Carmona et al. 2015). Thus, we hypothesized that drought would result in functionally impoverished communities, thereby supporting the physiological tolerance hypothesis that predicts a direct relation between productivity and functional diversity (Spasojevic et al. 2014). Some functional designs might disappear (lower α FD and TD) to result in higher functional similarity between the realized assemblages and a higher functional contribution of each assemblage to the total diversity (higher β FD and TD in terms of the contribution of each assemblage to the total diversity). Moreover, environmental variation over time should promote the maintenance of alternative functional strategies to those that are better adjusted to more frequent conditions. This could lead to functional complementarity among years (rainfall temporal niches), and thus to lower β FD and β TD (i.e. higher differences among assemblages; see the Methods for details of the β diversity index) and increased γ TD measured as the complete list of species observed over time (sum of all rainfall experimental scenarios).

Our expectations regarding the effects of biocrust disturbance are not straightforward because biocrusts are involved in multiple processes (Zhang et al. 2016, Havrilla et al. 2019). Biocrust disturbances can release germination and seedling establishment restrictions and lead to higher TD and FD during the first stages of community development. However, biocrusts provide different microhabitats for various species (Concostrina-Zubiri et al. 2014) and their disturbance may homogenize the spatial heterogeneity, thereby providing the basis for regenerative niche diversity to lower TD and FD. In addition, the effects of biocrusts on soil water

retention are still a matter of controversy, as both water retention improvement (Berdugo et al. 2014) and reduction has been reported (Kidron and Tal 2012, Xiao et al. 2019) probably as a function of the amount of crustose lichens able to seal the soil surface and the soil texture. Thus the interaction between biocrust and the different water availability scenarios may be complex.

In terms of PD and assuming trait conservatism (i.e. that closely related species are more functionally similar), the same patterns described above for FD are expected. However, trait convergence is also feasible due to the intense evolutionary restrictions imposed by the annual habit (Webb et al. 2002). In this case, a difference should emerge between FD and PD, and each dimension may provide a complementary community view (Swenson 2011).

Methods

Study system

The study system comprised annual plant communities that grow naturally on gypsum soils in central Spain (Fig. 1). In particular, soil monoliths were collected from a well-conserved gypsum steppe located in Ciempozuelos (40 km south of Madrid, 40°08'36.9"N, 3°36'60.0"W) at 568 m a.s.l., with a typical semiarid Mediterranean climate and annual mean rainfall of 365 mm m⁻². This habitat comprises gypsum specialized shrubs (*Helianthemum squamatum*, *Lepidium subulatum*, *Centaurea hyssopifolia* and *Gypsophila struthium*) scattered in a matrix of biocrusts, which are seasonally covered with a species rich annual plant community (ca 38 plant species/0.25 m²; Luzuriaga et al. 2012). The main species in this biocrust are crustose lichens such as *Diploschistes diacapsis*, *Squamarina lentigera*, *Fulgensia subbracteata* and *Psora decipiens*. The annuals are tiny plants (mean maximum height of 10.5 cm) that mostly germinate during the autumn and finish their life cycle before May. Some of the most frequent ephemeral species are *Alyssum simplex*, *Plantago afra* and *Micropyrum tenellum* as well as strict gypsophytes such as *Campanula fastigiata* (Luzuriaga et al. 2015) (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. From left to right, distribution of gypsum outcrops in the Iberian Peninsula (re-drawn from Escavy et al. 2012), and position of the study area (black star) in the Tajo Valley; general view of the study area where the monoliths were collected; and detailed picture of a strict gypsophile annual plant, *Campanula fastigiata*, growing on biological soil crust.

Sampling collection and establishment of community monoliths

We collected soil monoliths from open areas at least 50 cm away from perennial vegetation and with biocrust cover exceeding 50%. Each monolith comprised a surface square of 10 × 10 cm with a depth of 3 cm (Fig. 2) because most of the soil seed bank is confined in this layer (Peralta et al. 2016). The samples were extracted with a square core after watering the soil surface to facilitate biocrust conservation

and to avoid losing the soil's vertical structure. The soil monoliths were then placed on plastic trays and moved to the experimental station at Rey Juan Carlos University (Móstoles, Madrid, Spain; 40°18'48"N, 3°52'57"W) located 40 km west of the field site, but with a similar elevation and climate. Soil monoliths were collected in September 2013 and 2014 before autumn germination, and thus they contained the complete seed bank (i.e. seeds from the persistent seed bank and seeds dispersed in the previous spring).

Figure 2. Images showing the preparation of the annual grassland samples. 1–4: extraction of community monoliths before autumn rain. 5–6: arrangement of the monoliths in plastic pots filled with gypsum. 7–8: biocrust physical disturbance. 9: general view of the plots located below the rainout shelter. 10: example of a plastic pot containing a mature community in spring.

Four randomly selected monoliths ($10 \times 10 \times 3$ cm soil pieces) were carefully placed together in plastic pots with a diameter of 30 cm and depth of 10 cm, which were previously filled with 5 kg of gypsum soil containing no seeds obtained from a deep soil layer in the study area (Fig. 2). Broken or damaged soil pieces were discarded. The total soil surface area per pot was 20×20 cm, which was sufficiently representative in terms of the soil seed bank variability and micro-heterogeneity in this community (Peralta et al. 2016). We considered that each pot was a replicate of the community and an experimental unit. Pots were placed under the inner part of two rainout shelters (6 m long \times 5 m wide \times 2.4–2.0 m height) and 1 m away from its edges to avoid rainfall (Fig. 2).

Experimental design

In 2013, we conducted a first experiment to evaluate the effects of rainfall timing (three levels) and rainfall amount (two levels) according to an orthogonal experimental design, thereby resulting in six experimental rainfall scenarios (Supporting information). The rainfall timing treatments simulated the typical rainfall distribution (typical timing), a dry autumn with a wet spring (referred to as dry autumn in the following), and a wet autumn with a dry spring (dry spring). In addition, two rainfall amount levels were tested comprising the mean rainfall amount (270 mm during the growing period from October to April) and a slight drought treatment (25% rainfall reduction). The rainfall amount and timing in each treatment were based on rainfall data recorded at the nearest weather station in Getafe (<www.aemet.es>) from 1981 to 2010. The typical rainfall timing in our study area is characterized by wetter autumn than spring seasons (40% and 25% of the annual precipitation, respectively). Variability in this pattern is usual in Mediterranean systems and reductions in the rainfall amounts during the autumn or spring occur in 16% and 20% of the years, respectively. We experimentally reproduced both situations: dry autumn and dry spring. Thus, we calculated the separate rainfall amounts for autumn (October, November and December), winter (January) and spring (February, March and April). We then considered the mean rainfall in the five wettest springs and five wettest autumns and divided this quantity equally among the three spring/autumn months. In order to keep the annual rainfall constant, we fixed the January rainfall to 30 mm in all treatments and the remaining rainfall required to make 270 mm was divided among the three autumn/spring months. The typical rainfall distribution treatment was set as the mean rainfall for each season. Sixteen replicates per treatment combination were considered, thereby yielding 96 microcosm or experimental community replicates.

In 2014, we performed a second experiment to simultaneously evaluate the effects of biotic (biocrust disturbance) and abiotic (rainfall amount) factors on community assembly. We tested three rainfall levels and two biocrust treatments in an orthogonal design, with six scenarios. We used the same temporal rainfall distribution as the typical rainfall timing

treatment in experiment 1 and only manipulated the rainfall amount (not the timing). In particular, we established three rainfall treatments comprising mean rainfall with 100% of the mean rainfall recorded for every month during the reference period (1981–2010), and moderate and severe drought with rainfall reductions of 33% and 66% of the mean rainfall in every month, respectively. Two biocrust disturbance levels were tested: disturbed and intact. In the biocrust disturbance treatment, the biocrust structure was entirely destroyed with a mallet. The biocrust cover remains on the soil surface, as well as the soil seed bank, but shattered to small pieces (Fig. 2). In total, we tested 96 microcosms or experimental communities (16 community replicates \times 6 scenarios).

Irrigation was applied manually on a weekly basis with the appropriate water quantities for each month and scenario. The effects of the treatments in terms of the standardized soil water contents of the pots in each scenario were recorded in two pots per treatment and experiment with Hobo data loggers, as shown in the Supporting information.

Community monitoring and survey of species functional traits

We sampled species abundance in each experimental community unit three times in experiment 1 during December, February and April to evaluate the performance of seedling, vegetative and reproductive annuals, respectively. In experiment 2, we recorded plants in the seedling and reproductive stages. Additionally, we functionally characterized the observed species to measure shifts in functional diversity among the experimental communities. Species functional traits were estimated based on at least 10 healthy individuals per species, which were randomly collected in the same area where the soil monoliths were collected, according to the methods described by Cornelissen et al. (2003). We obtained functional trait data for about 90% of the annual species and individuals found in our experimental communities. We selected a set of non-correlated functional traits associated with the functional strategies of annual plants in order to delimit their niches and community assembly processes. In particular, we estimated the: 1) seed mass; 2) plant maximum height (omitting inflorescences); 3) specific leaf area (SLA); 4) leaf dry matter content (LDMC); 5) reproductive ratio (reproductive/vegetative dry mass ratio); and 6) root/shoot ratio (belowground/aboveground dry mass ratio). The seed mass is relevant to germination and seedling establishment. The SLA, LDMC and root/shoot ratio are related to drought resistance. In addition, the SLA, maximum plant height and reproductive/vegetative dry mass ratio are related to the growth rate, establishment of competitive hierarchies and resource allocation (Westoby et al. 2002).

DNA sequencing for community phylogeny analysis

Up to 20 mg of dry leaf samples per species were disrupted and homogenized using glass beads and a Tissue Lyser LT (Qiagen, Valencia, CA). Total genomic DNA was extracted

with a DNeasy Plant Mini-Kit (Qiagen, Valencia, CA) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Polymerase chain reactions (PCRs) were conducted to amplify the *rbcL* and *matK* loci in the chloroplast region. For amplification, 2 μ l of diluted DNA was added to 23 μ l of reaction mixture (2.5 μ l of Taq buffer 2 mM with $MgCl_2$, 1 μ l of dNTP Mix (0.4 mM), 1.25 μ l of forward and reverse primers and 1.25 U Taq DNA Polymerase (Biotools, Madrid, Spain)). PCR was performed with a S1000 Thermal Cycler using the primers and cycling program indicated in the Supporting information. The PCR products were cleaned up using ExoSap-IT (USB Corporation, Cleveland, OH, USA) and submitted to MacroGen Inc (Amsterdam, Netherlands) for sequencing in both directions with forward and reverse primers. The forward and reverse sequences were then assembled into contigs using Sequencher 4.1.4 (Genes Code Corporation) and deposited in GenBank (<www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/>). If it was not possible to extract DNA or obtain a valid PCR product for sequencing, the sequences were downloaded from GenBank (Supporting information).

The *rbcL* and *matK* consensus sequences were aligned independently using MAFFT ver. 7 and adjusted manually with MacClade (ver. 4.01, Sinauer). Ambiguous regions and introns were manually delimited and excluded from the phylogenetic analyses. *Dipcadi serotinum* (family Asparagaceae) was used as an outgroup based on previous phylogenies (Chase et al. 2016). Single-gene trees were obtained by maximum likelihood analysis with RAxML 8.0.24 (Stamatakis 2014) and the GTRCAT model with rapid bootstrapping. All analyses were conducted with CIPRES Science Gateway ver. 3.1 (Miller et al. 2010). We assessed the topological congruence of the two loci by comparing well-supported clades and considered a conflict significant among clades when a supported clade (bootstrap support ≥ 70) for one marker was contradicted by significant support for the other. No supported nodes were in conflict, so the data were combined into a single data matrix with two partitions: *rbcL* and *matK*. The concatenated data matrix contained 1433 unambiguously aligned nucleotides and it was employed for maximum likelihood analysis in the single gene analyses. The best tree obtained from the maximum likelihood analyses was used to calculate the PD indices.

Estimation of α , β and γ diversities and rarefaction curves

For every experimental unit and sampling time, we calculated two indices of taxonomic α diversity comprising the species richness (i.e. the total number of species within each unit, which we refer to as the species richness in the following) and the inverse Simpson diversity index (TD) as a richness measure weighted by species abundance. We also estimated phylogenetic and functional α diversity values using mean pairwise distance (MPD) indices. These indices represented the MPDs among species based on their functional (six traits) and phylogenetic positions, and they were independent of the species richness. MPDs were calculated using the 'melodic'

function in the vegan package in R (Oksanen et al. 2015). We also calculated the β diversity as the ratio between the inverse Simpson index (for TD) or MPD (for PD and FD) for each experimental unit and the corresponding index calculated for all experimental units for each treatment and sampling time. Consequently, this β index increased when the diversity of each sampling unit approached the diversity of all sampling units in each scenario, and thus we interpreted higher β diversities as denoting higher similarity among sampling units and vice versa. We also estimated two taxonomic γ diversity values comprising the treatment γ richness as the total number of species considering all the experimental communities under each treatment and sampling time, and the total γ richness per sampling time or community development stage by considering all treatments at each sampling time together. Thus, the α diversity represented the diversity within each experimental unit, the β diversity measured the contribution of each experimental unit to the total diversity in each treatment, and the γ diversity indicated the total diversity in each treatment. All of these local diversity measures reflected the fine spatial scale of variation in the realized assemblages of these tiny plants. We also produced rarefaction curves for every rainfall timing treatment in experiment 1 and every rainfall amount treatment (only with intact biocrust) in experiment 2 to confirm whether all of these scenarios were sufficiently representative of the community and that they contained the complete set of species in the plant community. We used the *rarefy* function in the vegan package in R (Oksanen et al. 2015).

Phylogenetic signals of functional traits

We calculated the phylogenetic signals for each of the six measured traits with the phytools package in R (Revell 2012). We used two different estimators comprising the K statistic of Blomberg and Pagel's λ by assuming a Brownian motion model of trait evolution. In the calculations, we used all of the species that appeared in experiment 1 and 2 as well as some other annuals found in communities that grow on gypsum soils in Ciempozuelos and other locations in the Tajo valley (Luzuriaga et al. 2018).

Data analyses

We used repeated measures generalized linear mixed models (GLMMs) to model the species richness, α and β TD, FD and PD. The rainfall timing, rainfall amount, life stage and interactions between them were used as fixed predictors in the first experiment. In the second experiment, the explanatory variables were the rainfall amount, biocrust disturbance, life stage and the interactions between them. We used the *glmer* function from the lme4 package in R (Bates et al. 2014) to fit the repeated measures models. We assumed Gaussian distributions and identity link functions for all the diversity indices. Pot was included in all analyses as a repeated measures random factor. We used the type III sum of squares obtained with the *car* function (Fox and Weisberg 2011).

Post hoc Tukey's tests were calculated with the lsmeans package (Lenth 2016).

Results

We registered more than 9300 individuals that belonged to 75 annual plant species and 26 families. The most abundant species were *Campanula erinus*, *Asterolinon linum-stellatum*, *Micropyrum tenellum*, *Erodium cicutarium* and *Plantago afra* (see Appendix S2 in the study by Peralta et al. 2019a). The phylogenetic tree obtained was congruent with recent phylogenies obtained for angiosperms (Chase et al. 2016). We detected significant phylogenetic signals for the root/shoot ratio with Blomberg's K estimator and for LDMC and reproductive/vegetative ratio with Pagel's λ estimator (Table 1).

Experiment 1

In the first experiment the γ richness ranged between 30 and 50 species per treatment and it was lower than the total γ richness per life stage (ca 60 species) (Fig. 3). Extrapolation of the rarefaction curves obtained similar results (Supporting information), thereby indicating that the complete list of species was not present in any treatment. Within each experimental assemblage, the (α) richness was constant throughout community development under the typical rainfall timing treatment, decreased in the dry spring treatment and increased from the seedling stage to the reproductive stage in the dry autumn treatment (Fig. 3, Supporting information).

The α and β TD values increased from the seedling to reproduction stages in most cases, especially under the dry autumn treatment (Table 2, Fig. 3). This pattern was also consistent for the α PD and α FD. The typical and dry spring rainfall treatments produced phylogenetically more diverse assemblages than the dry autumn treatment. However, the maximum α FD value was obtained under the typical rainfall timing. Reducing the mean rainfall by 25% had no effect on the FDs, and only marginal effects on β TD and α PD in the interaction with rainfall timing (Table 2).

Experiment 2

The total numbers of species recorded in each treatment and life stage (treatment γ richness) in the second experiment were lower than the total γ diversity per life stage, and similar to the numbers observed in experiment 1 (Fig. 4, Supporting information). Both moderate and severe droughts significantly reduced the richness of each experimental assemblage

(Fig. 4, Supporting information). Reducing the amount of rainfall by 33% and 66% also clearly decreased the α and β TD, PD and FD (Fig. 4, Table 2). All of the diversity metrics (α and β TD, PD and FD) were significantly affected by the interaction between life stage and biocrust (Table 2). In the seedling stage, the diversity tended to be higher when the biocrust was disturbed, but the diversity values were lower subsequently in the absence of a well conserved biocrust. This general decrease in the diversity when the biocrust was disturbed was particularly evident when the rainfall was reduced by 66% (life stage \times rainfall amount \times biocrust interaction in Table 2).

Discussion

The community experiments conducted in the present study showed a cause-effect relationships among the rain amount and timing and all α and β diversity components (TD, PD and FD). Higher rainfall amounts and rainfall timing closer to the typical pattern yielded more diverse communities, thereby supporting the physiological tolerance hypothesis (Spasojevic et al. 2014). Decreasing the water availability led to functionally (Stark et al. 2017) and phylogenetically simplified communities (Li et al. 2019). In addition, the alternative rainfall scenarios resulted in higher total gamma diversity because none of the treatments comprises the entire species pool (Levine and HilleRisLambers 2009). Together with rainfall scenarios, biocrust disturbance also exerted important effects on all dimensions of community diversity. Diversity loss was particularly evident when severe drought occurred simultaneously with biocrust disturbance. Therefore, these factors did not appear to operate independently but instead their combination produced new diversity profiles and community variations (Carmona et al. 2012, Spasojevic and Suding 2012) synergistically amplifying their individual effect.

Different rainfall timings promoted temporal niche differentiation and drought operated as an abiotic filter

As expected, the different experimental rainfall patterns resembling inter-year variability resulted in a higher number of species (γ diversity). Each treatment summed different species to the global species pool as can be deduced from the rarefaction curves (Supporting information). That means that each rain timing represented an opportunity for niche

Table 1. Phylogenetic signals in the flora of annual plant species that grow on gypsum soils in different location in the Tajo valley estimated with Pagel's λ and Blomberg's K estimators. The number of species (n) varied depending on the available information for each trait. P. height: plant height; Repr/Veg: reproductive-vegetative dry mass ratio; root/shoot: belowground-aboveground dry mass ratio; SLA: specific leaf area; LDMC: leaf dry matter content. Significant results are shown in bold and indicated by asterisks: '***' 0.001 < p < 0.01, '**' 0.01 < p < 0.05.

	P. height (n=99)	Repr/veg (n=98)	Root/shoot (n=98)	SLA (n=95)	LDMC (n=100)	Seed mass (n=88)
Blomberg's K	0.173	0.183	0.276*	0.209	0.175	0.131
Pagel's λ	0.161	0.157*	0.631	0.127	0.291**	6.70872e-05

Figure 3. Changes in taxonomic, phylogenetic and functional alpha and beta diversity, and alpha and gamma richness in experiment 1. The alpha diversity and richness represented the diversity within each experimental community, the beta diversity measured the contribution of each experimental community to the total diversity in each treatment, and the gamma richness indicated the total diversity in each treatment. The three rainfall timing treatments are shown (dry spring, typical timing and dry autumn) during community development from seedlings to vegetative adult and to reproductive adult plants. The rainfall amount treatment scenarios are not specifically shown because there were no significant differences between them. Vertical bars represent standard errors. Different letters represent least square mean differences among treatments tested with the post hoc Tukey's test.

differentiation over time in evolutionary terms and they allowed functionally rare species to be incorporated in the realized assemblages (Levine et al. 2011), thereby resulting in novel taxonomic configurations and higher species richness (Levine and HilleRisLambers 2009).

The typical rainfall pattern produced the most diverse communities. However, it seems that the dry autumn and dry spring treatments provided regeneration opportunities (i.e. new niche options) for some species that are usually part of the hidden diversity in the permanent soil seed bank (Levine et al. 2011). The persistence of dormant seeds in the soil seed bank is a general strategy that allows annuals in drylands to cope with environmental stochasticity (i.e. bet hedging; Clausen and Venable 2000). Thus, the temporal variability and unpredictability in rainfall patterns is a key factor that can induce alternative assembly scenarios and enhance the appearance of alternative functional designs (Violle et al. 2017).

The different effects on assembly of autumn and spring droughts suggest that germination cues are the main sources of niche differentiation during the assembly of these plant

communities (Jiménez-Alfaro et al. 2016), thereby highlighting the importance of so-called regeneration niche differences (Grubb 1977). These differential effects may have been related to the major role of autumn germination compared with spring germination in the Mediterranean Basin (Carmona et al. 2015). Spring germination represented a minor percentage of the total germination (around 10% in this study), but it had important effects on all types of diversity observed in the reproductive community stage. The spring germination pulse might rely on species that are already present in the realized assemblage, but also on the germination of other species that respond specifically to these environmental germination cues (Sánchez et al. 2014). Spring germinating species entering the vegetation from the soil seed bank may explain the increased richness, TD, PD and FD. For instance, *Chaenorhinum reyessii* and *Campanula fastigiata* (Fig. 1) are examples of species that mainly germinate after the low winter temperatures pass. These species are characterized by tiny size and rapid development (usually < 5 cm in maximum height), which allow them to complete their whole life cycle in a couple

Table 2. Generalized linear mixed models (GLMMs) used to explain variability in plant taxonomic, phylogenetic and functional alpha and beta diversity. The alpha diversity represented the diversity within each experimental unit and the beta diversity measured the contribution of each experimental unit to the total diversity in each treatment. In experiment 1, the community life stage, rainfall timing, rainfall amount and their interactions were included in the models as fixed effects. In experiment 2, the community life stage, rainfall amount, biocrust disturbance (biocrust) and their interactions were included in the models as fixed effects. Pot was also included in all models as a repeated measures random factor. Significant results are shown in bold and indicated by asterisks: '****' $p < 0.001$, '***' $0.001 < p < 0.01$, '**' $0.01 < p < 0.05$, '.' $0.05 < p < 0.1$.

	df	Taxonomic		Phylogenetic		Functional	
		Alpha χ^2	Beta χ^2	Alpha χ^2	Beta χ^2	Alpha χ^2	Beta χ^2
Experiment 1							
Intercept	1	274.71***	296.85***	2231.97***	2218.34***	1907.71***	1853.43***
Life stage (S)	2	9.23**	10.05**	55.16***	55.05***	13.49**	13.21**
Rainfall timing (T)	2	5.67.	5.13.	7.37*	4.06	9.10*	5.03.
Rainfall amount (A)	1	1.06	0.04	0.44	0.69	1.54	0.00
S × T	4	13.32**	15.29**	5.11	5.52	6.52	6.21
S × A	2	0.29	0.22	2.93	2.95	1.52	1.84
T × A	2	1.5	7.45*	6.63*	4.78.	5.54.	5.22.
S × T × A	4	2.26	5.16	0.74	0.72	0.42	0.31
Experiment 2							
Intercept	1	522.7***	464.38***	3967.82***	3787.19***	2482.76***	2372.18***
Life stage (S)	1	0.36	0.11	1.13	0.97	2.77.	2.07
Rainfall amount (A)	2	66.53***	11.81**	40.55***	14.68***	41.81***	8.59*
Biocrust	1	0.58	0.07	0.33	0.14	0.08	0.16
S × A	2	2.55	3.80	0.17	0.13	3.73	3.28
S × Biocrust	1	13.51***	13.57***	3.91*	4.15*	9.11**	9.94**
A × Biocrust	2	3.74	1.62	4.69.	1.26	1.32	1.72
S × A × Biocrust	2	5.97.	5.20.	15.63***	15.98***	16.65***	18.00***

of months, and by their ability to establish directly on crustose lichens to exploit a microhabitat where interference and competition with other annuals is low. In fact, these species are strict gypsophytes and highly specialized so they can thrive on this selective gypsum microhabitat (Luzuriaga et al. 2015).

After reducing the amount of rainfall, we found a degree of resilience to drought in the community, which is a similar type of community adaptation (sensu Aubree et al. 2020) to that observed in other Mediterranean (Tielbörger et al. 2014) and infertile grasslands (Grime et al. 2008). Slight and moderate droughts (25% and 33% rainfall reduction) were not sufficiently severe to produce changes in α and β TD, PD and FD. However, severe drought (66% rainfall reduction) operated as a critical abiotic filter inducing a generalized decrease in all types of diversity in both the seedling and reproductive stages. During the seedling stage, processes other than abiotic filtering which are compatible with reductions in FD and PD (Mayfield and Levine 2010) could have played minor roles, e.g. competitive exclusion due to fitness differences. Under these very stressful conditions, only the species with better adaptations to drought were able to germinate and enter the community (Peralta et al. 2019a). Consequently, the species richness and diversity decreased following the well-known direct relation between productivity and FD (Spasojevic et al. 2014). The change in the β diversity was similar, and thus each realized assemblage under intense drought conditions was an impoverished representation of the total diversity in each treatment.

Biocrust disturbance enhanced germination but compromised all of the diversity dimensions

Biocrust disturbance had clear effects on all types of diversity during community development. In general, the α diversity values in the seedling stage were higher when the biocrust was disturbed, whereas the opposite was found in the mature plant stage. Thus, the biocrust may have acted as a biotic filter by excluding certain functions from the realized assemblages in the earliest stages (Peralta et al. 2019a). Previous studies showed that seedling emergence was reduced in the presence of intact biocrusts (Prasse and Bornkamm 2000), but the magnitude of the effect depended on both the identity of the dominant lichen species and the annual species involved (Escudero et al. 2007). Biocrusts on semiarid gypsum soils mainly comprise crustose lichens such as *Diploschistes diacapsis* and *Squamarina lentigera*. These species are quite different in terms of their roughness but both have a hard thallus that is difficult for the roots of seedlings to penetrate and this limits the performance of most plant species in early stages (Romão and Escudero 2005). This effect is consistent with the increased seedling diversity found after biocrust disturbance. Indeed, our results demonstrated the great importance of the physical effect of the biocrust compared with its chemical effect because its disturbance increased seedling emergence even when lichen exudates remained in the soil (Escudero et al. 2015). Our results did not support a role for biocrust as a source of spatial niche differentiation but this possibility cannot be rejected completely in our opinion

Figure 4. Changes in taxonomic, phylogenetic and functional alpha and beta diversities, and alpha and gamma richness in experiment 2 during community development, from seedlings to reproductive adult plants. The alpha diversity and richness represented the diversity within each experimental community, the beta diversity measured the contribution of each experimental community to the total diversity in each treatment, and the gamma richness indicated the total diversity in each treatment. The three rainfall amount treatments (100% mean rainfall, 33% rainfall reduction, 66% rainfall reduction) and biological soil crust disturbance treatments (intact BSC, disturbed BSC) are shown. Vertical bars represent standard errors. Different letters represent least square mean differences among treatments tested with the post hoc Tukey's test.

because of the following reasons. First, niche segregation could have operated at a larger spatial scale, such as when comparing patches with and without biocrusts. Second, in order to detect the existence of niche differentiation relative to the micro-environmental heterogeneity caused by the species composition in the biocrust, more detailed manipulations should be performed to investigate the specific effects of the different dominant lichen species in the crust on each plant species in the community (Escudero et al. 2007).

One of our most striking results was the radical shift observed in the annuals–biocrust relationship during the ontogeny of annuals from the filtering effect exerted by the biocrust on germination to a positive effect on adult plant growth and survival. The presence of a well-conserved biocrust enhanced the development of annual species during the community life stages and promoted the maintenance of diversity. Positive effects of biocrusts on plant recruitment and growth have been reported previously (Havrilla et al. 2019). Moreover, previous studies on our study area showed that the biocrust enhances water gain and retention relative to bare ground surfaces (Berdugo et al. 2014), an effect very

likely dependent on biocrust composition, soil type and rain patterns. The absence of these positive effects in the biocrust disturbed treatments prevented some annual plant functional designs from surviving until spring when the higher temperatures increased evapotranspiration. This effect was especially remarkable in drier scenarios where the realized assemblages were particularly degraded and collapsed when the biocrust was disturbed. By contrast, the intact biocrust ameliorated the conditions in the driest scenarios and the diversity values were similar to those observed under the wetter treatments.

Diversity changes during community development

The plant communities were dynamic, and the species compositions varied over time from germination to the reproductive stage due to the temporal sequence of processes that determined species recruitment and coexistence. The rainfall pattern and biocrust both operated as filters on seed germination and seedling establishment. Subsequently, the diversity values remained constant under the typical rainfall scenario without spring drought, thereby reflecting at the phenological

peak the values found during the germination stage. Annuals in the Mediterranean are well equipped to survive the freezing temperatures that occur frequently during the winter after autumn germination (Kimball et al. 2010, Pescador et al. 2018). Even in more benign conditions, species interactions did not result in competitive exclusion and the diversity remained constant during community development, or it even increased slightly, probably because of the low primary productivity of these habitats (Escudero et al. 2015) and the fact that the whole community restarting every year from the soil seed bank prevents more competitive species from occupying space or resources. These findings demonstrate the importance of regeneration traits for the assembly of these communities (Jiménez-Alfaro et al. 2016). Moreover, the annual biotype can be regarded as a successful ecological strategy that allow species to avoid summer drought, but it also provides a flexible template (the soil seed bank) so the community can adjust to the shifting climatic conditions each year.

Did the diversity components respond consistently to drivers of global change?

The three diversity components responded consistently to the rainfall amount and timing, and biocrust disturbance. The α TD, PD and FD decreased under the dry autumn treatment in experiment 1, and although TD recovered during community development, the species remained more functionally similar and phylogenetically related than those under the typical rainfall timing. In experiment 2, under extremely severe drought, all of the diversity dimensions were affected, and simplified assemblages were produced in terms of the species, functions and phylogenetic distance. Moreover, extreme drought also reduced β TD, PD and FD, and a poorer representation of the species pool was found in each community replicate. Thus, although the phylogenetic diversity is linked to long-term evolutionary processes (Webb et al. 2002), we found causal relationships with ecological factors. Furthermore, PD and FD responded to the different environmental scenarios in a consistent manner. These results agreed with the phylogenetic signals observed for the LDMC, root/shoot ratio and reproductive/vegetative ratio. However, in general, the reduced number of phylogenetic signals suggested the importance of additional traits to those considered in this study, and also of factors that are not related to the phylogenetic history for trait evolution. Annuals communities in Israel also exhibited the same trend (García-Camacho et al. 2017). Therefore, the absence of phylogenetic signals for some of the functional traits may have been related to the strong restriction imposed by the annual habit leading to trait convergence independent of the evolutionary origin.

Severe drought and biocrust disturbance drastically affected the communities investigated in the present study. If the extreme droughts considered in our experiment increase in frequency, some species could appear less frequently or even become locally extinct. This hypothetical but not unlikely scenario based on climatic models (Barros and Field 2014)

would lead to the functionally based filtering of species, and thus to functionally and phylogenetically simplified communities. Biocrust destruction is also an ongoing and critical global change scenario in drylands (Reed et al. 2016), as shown previously in observational (Concostrina-Zubiri et al. 2014, Eldridge and Delgado-Baquerizo 2019) and experimental studies (Escolar et al. 2012, Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2014, 2016). The simultaneous occurrence of both climate change and biocrust destruction could have particularly negative effects on the diversity of these communities which sustain a very important fraction of the total plant diversity of drylands.

However, in order to scale up these findings to larger spatial and temporal scales, and to obtain realistic local and regional predictions for the mid-term fate of these communities, we must consider the following two factors. First, the existence of greater environmental heterogeneity at local and regional scales may provide a wider range of niches (Harrison et al. 2020) than the considered in this study. Second, the bet hedging role of the soil seed bank allows species to disperse over time. These factors suggest that these communities are very resilient. Indeed, we previously observed how rapidly the vegetation (Luzuriaga et al. 2012) and seed banks (Olano et al. 2012) recovered at fine spatial scales after extreme drought and drastic disturbance, respectively.

Conclusions

Our results showed that the temporal environmental heterogeneity due to interannual variability in the amount and timing of rainfall as well as the presence of biocrust greatly determined the assembly of annual communities in the Mediterranean. Variations in these factors may enhance regeneration niche differentiation and could have led to changes in the establishment hierarchy of species according to differences in their relative fitness. We also showed that some global change scenarios such as extreme droughts and especially their interaction with biocrust disturbance decreased the number of species and functional designs in the community, but also reduced the number of plant lineages. This simplification of the annual plant communities under the stressful conditions related to global change implies evolutionary and ecological heritage losses that can permanently compromise the stability of communities under uncertain and changeable environmental conditions.

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Author contributions

Ana M. Sánchez and **Ana M. L. Peralta** are both first authors. **Ana M. Sánchez**: Conceptualization (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – original draft (lead); Writing – review and editing (lead). **Ana M. L. Peralta**: Formal analysis (lead); Investigation (lead); Methodology (equal); Writing – original draft (supporting); Writing – review and editing (supporting). **Arantzazu L. Luzuriaga**: Conceptualization (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – original draft (supporting); Writing – review and editing (supporting). **María Prieto**: Formal analysis (supporting); Writing – original draft (supporting); Writing – review and editing (supporting). **Adrián Escudero**: Conceptualization (equal); Funding acquisition (lead); Methodology (equal); Writing – original draft (supporting); Writing – review and editing (supporting).

Data availability statement

Data available from the Dryad Digital Repository: <<https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.tf7s2s5>> (Peralta et al. 2019b).

Supporting information

The supporting information associated with this article is available from the online version.

References

- Adler, P. B. et al. 2013. Trait-based tests of coexistence mechanisms. – *Ecol. Lett.* 16: 1294–1306.
- Aubree, F. et al. 2020. How community adaptation affects biodiversity–ecosystem functioning relationships. – *Ecol. Lett.* 23: 1263–1275.
- Barros, V. R. and Field, C. B. 2014. Part A: global and sectoral aspects. (Contribution of working group II to the fifth assessment report of the intergovernmental panel on climate change). *Climate change 2014: impacts, adaptation and vulnerability*, 1132. – <www.ipcc.ch/pdf/assessment-report/ar5/wg2/WGI-IAR5-FrontMatterA_FINAL.pdf>.
- Bates, D. et al. 2014. lme4: linear mixed effects models using Eigen and S4. – R package ver. 1.1-7. <<http://CRAN.R-project.org/package=lme4>>.
- Berdugo, M. et al. 2014. Vascular plants and biocrusts modulate how abiotic factors affect wetting and drying events in drylands. – *Ecosystems* 17: 1242–1256.
- Carmona, C. P. et al. 2012. Taxonomical and functional diversity turnover in Mediterranean grasslands: interactions between grazing, habitat type and rainfall. – *J. App. Ecol.* 49: 1084–1093.
- Carmona, C. P. et al. 2015. Inter-annual fluctuations in rainfall shift the functional structure of Mediterranean grasslands across gradients of productivity and disturbance. – *J. Veg. Sci.* 26: 538–551.
- Chamizo, S. et al. 2012. Crust composition and disturbance drive infiltration through biological soil crusts in semiarid ecosystems. – *Ecosystems* 15: 148–161.
- Chase, M. W. et al. 2016. An update of the Angiosperm Phylogeny Group classification for the orders and families of flowering plants: APG IV. – *Bot. J. Linn. Soc.* 181: 1–20.
- Chesson, P. 2000. Mechanisms of maintenance of species diversity. – *Annu. Rev. Ecol. Evol. Syst.* 31: 343–358.
- Clauss, M. J. and Venable, D. L. 2000. Seed germination in desert annuals: an empirical test of adaptive bet hedging. – *Am. Nat.* 155: 168–186.
- Concostrina-Zubiri, L. et al. 2014. Climate and small scale factors determine functional diversity shifts of biological soil crusts in Iberian drylands. – *Biodivers. Conserv.* 23: 1757–1770.
- Cornelissen, J. H. C. et al. 2003. A handbook of protocols for standardised and easy measurement of plant functional traits worldwide. – *Austral. J. Bot.* 51: 335–380.
- Delgado-Baquerizo, M. et al. 2014. Direct and indirect impacts of climate change on microbial and biocrust communities alter the resistance of the N cycle in a semiarid grassland. – *J. Ecol.* 102: 1592–1605.
- Delgado-Baquerizo, M. et al. 2016. Biocrust-forming mosses mitigate the negative impacts of increasing aridity on ecosystem multifunctionality in drylands. – *New Phytol.* 209: 1540–1552.
- Elbert, W. et al. 2012. Contribution of cryptogamic covers to the global cycles of carbon and nitrogen. – *Nat. Geosci.* 5: 459–462.
- Eldridge, D. J. and Delgado-Baquerizo, M. 2019. The influence of climatic legacies on the distribution of dryland biocrust communities. – *Global Change Biol.* 25: 327–336.
- Eldridge, D. J. et al. 2010. Interactive effects of three ecosystem engineers on infiltration in a semi-arid Mediterranean grassland. – *Ecosystems* 13: 499–510.
- Escavy, J. I. et al. 2012. Gypsum resources of Spain: temporal and spatial distribution. – *Ore Geol. Rev.* 49: 72–84.
- Escolar, C. et al. 2012. Warming reduces the growth and diversity of biological soil crusts in a semi-arid environment: implications for ecosystem structure and functioning. – *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. B* 367: 3087–3099.
- Escudero, A. et al. 2007. Soil lichens have species-specific effects on the seedling emergence of three gypsophile plant species. – *J. Arid Environ.* 70: 18–28.
- Escudero, A. et al. 2015. Plant life on gypsum: a review of its multiple facets. – *Biol. Rev.* 90: 1–18.
- Fox, J. and Weisberg, S. 2019. *An R companion to applied regression*, 3rd edn. – Sage, Thousand Oaks, CA.
- García-Camacho, R. et al. 2017. Phylogenetic structure of annual plant communities along an aridity gradient. Interacting effects of habitat filtering and shifting plant–plant interactions. – *Isr. J. Plant Sci.* 64: 122–134.
- Gerhold, P. et al. 2015. Phylogenetic patterns are not proxies of community assembly mechanisms (they are far better). – *Funct. Ecol.* 29: 600–614.
- González-Orozco, C. E. et al. 2016. Phylogenetic approaches reveal biodiversity threats under climate change. – *Nat. Clim. Change* 6: 1110–1114.
- Graham, C. H. and Fine, P. V. A. 2008. Phylogenetic beta diversity: linking ecological and evolutionary processes across space in time. – *Ecol. Lett.* 11: 1265–1277.

- Grime, J. P. et al. 2008. Long-term resistance to simulated climate change in an infertile grassland. – *Proc. Natl Acad. Sci. USA* 105: 10028–10032.
- Grubb, P. J. 1977. The maintenance of species-richness in plant communities: the importance of the regeneration niche. – *Biol. Rev.* 52: 107–145.
- Harrison, S. et al. 2018. Climate-driven diversity change in annual grasslands: drought plus deluge does not equal normal. – *Global Change Biol.* 24: 1782–1792.
- Harrison, S. et al. 2020. Climate and plant community diversity in space and time. – *Proc. Natl Acad. Sci. USA* 117: 4464–4470.
- Havrilla, C. A. et al. 2019. Towards a predictive framework for biocrust mediation of plant performance: a meta-analysis. – *J. Ecol.* 107: 2789–2807.
- HilleRisLambers, J. et al. 2012. Rethinking community assembly through the lens of coexistence theory. – *Annu. Rev. Ecol. Evol. Syst.* 43: 227–248.
- Jiménez-Alfaro, B. et al. 2016. Seed germination traits can contribute better to plant community ecology. – *J. Veg. Sci.* 27: 637–645.
- Kidron, G. J. 2019. The dual effect of sand-covered biocrusts on annual plants: increasing cover but reducing individual plant biomass and fecundity. – *Catena* 182: 104120.
- Kidron, G. J. and Tal, S. Y. 2012. The effect of biocrusts on evaporation from sand dunes in the Negev Desert. – *Geoderma* 179: 104–112.
- Kimball, S. et al. 2010. Contemporary climate change in the Sonoran Desert favors cold-adapted species. – *Global Change Biol.* 16: 1555–1565.
- Lenth, R. V. 2016. Least-squares means: the R package lsmeans. – *J. Stat. Softw.* 69: 1–33.
- Levine, J. M. and HilleRisLambers, J. 2009. The importance of niches for the maintenance of species diversity. – *Nature* 461: 254–257.
- Levine, J. M. et al. 2011. Seasonal timing of first rain storms affects rare plant population dynamics. – *Ecology* 92: 2236–2247.
- Li, D. et al. 2019. Climate drives loss of phylogenetic diversity in a grassland community. – *Proc. Natl Acad. Sci. USA* 116: 19989–19994.
- López-Angulo, J. et al. 2020. Impacts of climate, soil and biotic interactions on the interplay of the different facets of alpine plant diversity. – *Sci. Total Environ.* 698: 133960.
- Luzuriaga, A. L. et al. 2012. Assemblage of a semi-arid annual plant community: abiotic and biotic filters act hierarchically. – *PLoS One* 7: e41270.
- Luzuriaga, A. L. et al. 2015. Annual plant community assembly in edaphically heterogeneous environments. – *J. Veg. Sci.* 26: 866–875.
- Luzuriaga, A. L. et al. 2018. Habitat fragmentation determines diversity of annual plant communities at landscape and fine spatial scales. – *Basic Appl. Ecol.* 29: 12–19.
- Mayfield, M. M. and Levine, J. M. 2010. Opposing effects of competitive exclusion on the phylogenetic structure of communities. – *Ecol. Lett.* 13: 1085–1093.
- Miller, M. A. et al. 2010. Creating the CIPRES Science Gateway for inference of large phylogenetic trees. – In: *Proc. of the gateway computing environments workshop (GCE)*, pp. 1–8.
- Oksanen, J. et al. 2015. *Vegan: community ecology package.* – R package ver. 2.3-2. – <http://CRAN.R-project.org/package=vegan>.
- Olano, J. M. et al. 2012. Soil seed bank recovery occurs more rapidly than expected in semi-arid Mediterranean gypsum vegetation. – *Ann. Bot.* 109: 299–307.
- Peralta, A. M. L. et al. 2016. Factors driving species assemblage in Mediterranean soil seed banks: from the large to the fine scale. – *Ann. Bot.* 117: 1221–1228.
- Peralta, A. M. L. et al. 2019a. Evidence of functional species sorting by rainfall and biotic interactions: a community monolith experimental approach. – *J. Ecol.* 107: 2772–2788.
- Peralta, M. L. et al. 2019b. Data from: Evidence of functional species sorting by rainfall and biotic interactions: a community monolith experimental approach. – *Dryad*, <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.tf7s2s5>.
- Pescador, D. S. et al. 2018. Winter is coming: plant freezing resistance as a key functional trait for the assembly of annual Mediterranean communities. – *Ann. Bot.* 121: 335–344.
- Prasse, R. and Bornkamm, R. 2000. Effect of microbiotic soil surface crusts on emergence of vascular plants. – *Plant Ecol.* 150: 65–75.
- Purschke, O. et al. 2013. Contrasting changes in taxonomic, phylogenetic and functional diversity during a long-term succession: insights into assembly processes. – *J. Ecol.* 101: 857–866.
- Reed, S. C. et al. 2016. Biocrusts in the context of global change. – In: *Weber, B. et al. (eds), Biological soil crusts: an organizing principle in drylands. Ecological Studies (Analysis and Synthesis)*, vol. 226. Springer, pp. 451–476.
- Revell, L. J. 2012. Phytools: an R package for phylogenetic comparative biology (and other things). – *Methods Ecol. Evol.* 3: 217–223.
- Rodríguez-Caballero, E. et al. 2018. Dryland photoautotrophic soil surface communities endangered by global change. – *Nat. Geosci.* 11: 185–189.
- Romão, R. L. and Escudero, A. 2005. Gypsum physical soil crusts and the existence of gypsophytes in semi-arid central Spain. – *Plant Ecol.* 181: 127–137.
- Sánchez, A. M. et al. 2014. Environmental control of germination in semi-arid Mediterranean systems: the case of annuals on gypsum soils. – *Seed Sci. Res.* 24: 247–256.
- Shiple, B. et al. 2016. Reinforcing loose foundation stones in trait-based plant ecology. – *Oecologia* 180: 923–931.
- Spasojevic, M. J. and Suding, K. N. 2012. Inferring community assembly mechanisms from functional diversity patterns: the importance of multiple assembly processes. – *J. Ecol.* 100: 652–661.
- Spasojevic, M. J. et al. 2014. Ontogenetic trait variation influences tree community assembly across environmental gradients. – *Ecosphere* 5: 1–20.
- Stamatakis, A. 2014. RAXML ver. 8: a tool for phylogenetic analysis and post-analysis of large phylogenies. – *Bioinformatics* 30: 1312–1313.
- Stark, J. et al. 2017. Does environmental heterogeneity drive functional trait variation? A test in montane and alpine meadows. – *Oikos* 126: 1650–1659.
- Stein, A. et al. 2014. Environmental heterogeneity as a universal driver of species richness across taxa, biomes and spatial scales. – *Ecol. Lett.* 17: 866–880.
- Swenson, N. G. 2011. The role of evolutionary processes in producing biodiversity patterns, and the interrelationships between taxonomic, functional and phylogenetic biodiversity. – *Am. J. Bot.* 98: 472–480.
- Tielbörger, K. et al. 2014. Middle-Eastern plant communities tolerate 9 years of drought in a multi-site climate manipulation experiment. – *Nat. Commun.* 5: 5102.

- Violle, C. et al. 2017. Functional rarity: the ecology of outliers. – *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 32: 356–367.
- Webb, C. O. et al. 2002. Phylogenies and community ecology. – *Annu. Rev. Ecol. Syst.* 33: 475–505.
- Westoby, M. et al. 2002. Plant ecological strategies: some leading dimensions of variation between species. – *Annu. Rev. Ecol. Syst.* 33: 125–159.
- Xiao, B. et al. 2019. Biocrusts reduce surface soil infiltrability and impede soil water infiltration under tension and ponding conditions in dryland ecosystem. – *J. Hydrol.* 568: 792–802.
- Zhang, Y. et al. 2016. Interactions of biological soil crusts with vascular plants. – In: *Biological soil crusts: an organizing principle in drylands*. Springer, pp. 385–406.